

SYNCHRONIZATION OF SPATIALLY DISTRIBUTED MEASUREMENTS

A method for synchronizing multichannel measurements on objects distributed in space is presented. The task of multichannel measurements and registration of various diagnostic information in the form of synchronous digital samples is typical for many diagnostic tasks.

We consider a system consisting of several local diagnostic information recorders, for example, from a group of acoustic or vibration sensors. Using subsequent cross-correlation processing of the recorded data, it is possible to determine the coordinates of various sources of acoustic noise and vibration.

The most important requirement for a recording system is to ensure synchronous recording of signal samples. Synchronization of measurements between signals connected to the same recorder is ensured with high accuracy by using the same electrical timing signal. To ensure synchronization of the recording of signal samples by different recorders, a wireless synchronization system is required.

The developed synchronization system has two levels of synchronization: coarse (about 1 second) and fine (no worse than 100 microseconds). All recorders have a radio receiver (for example, analog transceiver Kenwood TK-2206, 400-470 MHz). Radios are programmed for a specific frequency range and user group code. A separate starting (command) radio station operates on the same frequency range and transmits the user group code. This is a built-in feature of such radios.

Recorders begin recording signals from sensors after a signal from the starting radio station appears. Due to the variation in detector parameters, the variation in the start time of different recorder instances can reach 1 second. This is "rough" synchronization.

To reduce the error, the correlation method is used. The starting command radio transmits a reference analog noise-like signal of 200 – 4000 Hz for 10 seconds. This signal is received by recorders, digitized and recorded in output arrays along with signals from sensors.

The recorded arrays are saved in the recorders as files. During the subsequent joint processing of records from different recorders, the time shift of the original records is first determined from the reference noise signal received over the radio channel using cross-correlation processing, followed by compensation for the time shift between the signals from the sensors. It is practically confirmed that the error of "precise" synchronization does not exceed 100 μ s.

The presented synchronization system is integrated at the hardware and software [1] levels into the RASTR system, which is designed for diagnosing long underground pipelines using correlation parametric methods [2].

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1. Владимирський ОА, Владимирський І.А., Артемчук В.О. Комп'ютерна програма «Багатоканальний реєстратор «Вібрологгер - 3.02» системи виявлення витоків підземних трубопроводів «РАСТР-2В». Заява ПІМЕ ім. Г.Є. Пухова НАН України про реєстрацію авторського права на твір № с202409803 від 02.12.2024р
2. Vladimirsky A. A., Vladimirsky I. A. Correlation parametric methods for determining the coordinates of leaks in underground pipelines. *Electronic modeling*. 2021. Vol. 43, № 3. P. 03–16. URL: <https://doi.org/10.15407/emodel.43.03.003> (date of access: 1.10.2024).

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